

ANALYSIS OF THE PRODUCTION AND SALE OF FINISHED PRODUCTS OF THE ENTERPRISE

G.A.Khayitboyeva

Assistant of the Department of General Economic Disciplines at TSUE

Annotation. *Today, the production and sale of finished products (works, services) is the main attribute of activity. It can also be said that this is the main source of income for any organization. It is during the process of selling finished products that the final stage of the business cycle begins. The reliability and correctness of determining the financial result of all the company's activities depends on how the company determines the financial result from the sale of finished products.*

Key words: *economics, accounting, balance sheet, capital, tax, products, organizations, analysis*

Introduction. The growth rate of production and sales, and quality improvement directly affect the amount of costs, profits, and profitability. The activities of business entities should be aimed at producing and selling the maximum amount of high-quality products at minimal cost. Therefore, it is important to conduct an analysis of production, which will identify the most significant increase in output and improvement of its quality, to determine the internal reserves of production growth.

The task of the organization is to ensure the demand of the population with high-quality products. Information about the demand for specific types of goods will allow the organization to respond more quickly to the consumer's request and determine the level of competitiveness. Profit depends on the volume of production and sales, the quality of products and the corresponding requirements of consumers. If the deadlines for implementation are not met, the organization pays fines for violation of contractual obligations.

Each organization reflects in its accounting policy the main methods of accounting for finished products, since this is required for accurate and timely accounting of financial results, on which many indicators of the organization's activities depend, the main of which is the amount of tax and the amount of net profit. The correspondence of accounts and valuation depends on the method used to generate production costs and on the moment of transfer of ownership of the products sold, as determined by the purchase and sale agreement. At the end of each month, the financial result from the sale is determined on the basis of documents confirming the sale of products. The correctness of determining the financial result from the sale depends on the validity of the formation of the price and the cost of the products sold.

Literature review. In these conditions, the main importance is given to the sale of products under supply contracts – one of the main performance indicators that determine the effectiveness and expediency of an enterprise's business activities. Since enterprises acquire independence in a market economy and bear full responsibility for the results of their production and entrepreneurial activities to their owners and employees, a direct link between efficiency is revealed. production and business activities and the organization of the accounting system at the enterprise. It is also important to properly organize the accounting of finished products, their shipment and sale.

In the following years, significant adjustments are made to the current tax and accounting legislation. The informatization of the world economy also has a huge impact on all changes, which leads to the development of modern information technologies and the worldwide computer network Internet, the spread of "electronic finance" and "e-commerce". In the coming years, this trend will only intensify, as the information itself has become global and versatile in volume, huge in scale, continuous in time.

The conducted research shows that the development of accounting does not stand still, and gradually accounting policy has become a section of accounting that is often mentioned in the regulatory framework. The requirements for accounting policy are only increasing. In the conditions of a global market economy, accounting information is necessary to ensure competent, accurate management of the organization's activities, analysis and control over the state of economic assets and sources, the results of economic activity and the safety of property. To successfully keep records in any organization, you need to know the basics of its construction.

Analysis. The analysis of production and sales of products has a great impact on the result of the economic activity of the organization. With the help of analysis, development trends are studied, factors of changes in performance are investigated, plans and management decisions are justified, their implementation is monitored, reserves for improving production efficiency are identified, and the results of the organization's activities are evaluated. The purpose of analyzing the sale of finished products is to identify ways to increase sales volumes compared to competitors, expand market share while maximizing production capacity and, as a result, increase the net profit of the organization.[1]

Figure 1 – Movement of finished products[2]

The information base for the analysis of product sales is the data contained in accounting statements, statistical reports, information contained in the accounting policy of the organization, the profit and loss statement, and explanations to the

accounting statements. They also include information contained in the accounts for the accounting of output, sales and finished products, warehouse accounting data, production information, data on the movement of finished products between warehouses and its sale.

When analyzing changes in the plan and dynamics of production and sale of finished products by different workshops and sites, the necessary information can be obtained from the company's budget data, production plans and reports on finished products, profit and loss statements, notes to accounting statements and appendices to them. The main task of analyzing the sale of finished products is to analyze the position of the organization and its ability to use resources when the market changes. The growth rate of production and sales of products, improvement of their quality directly affect the amount of costs, profit and profitability of the enterprise.

The process of selling finished products consists of four periods:[3]

- conclusion of a contract with customers for the supply;
- preparation of a sales plan and sale to a warehouse;
- shipment of finished products to customers;
- receipt of funds to the organization's current account. The release of finished products is a key stage in the production activity of an organization, without which its main goal is impossible – making a profit.

The methodology of financial condition analysis is based on certain principles, methods and sequence of analysis. In the analysis of economic activity, the methodology is a set of analytical methods and rules for researching the activities of an organization. The whole set of methods and techniques of economic analysis is used to implement the stages of the methodology of analysis of production and sale of products. It is traditional to use analytical tables to conduct structural and dynamic analysis and identify trends.

The comparison method allows you to evaluate the work of an organization, identify deviations and identify their causes. With this method, the indicators for the current period are compared with those for the previous period, as well as the comparison takes place with the average industry data. Using a specific method, you can analyze the relationship between price and sales volume for a certain type of product. Using this method, you can consider how one indicator changes from another, allows you to draw a relationship between them and find out how they are related to each other.

The information base for the analysis of product sales is the data contained in the accounting statements, statistical reports, information contained in the accounting policy of the organization, notes to the accounting statements. They also include information contained in the accounts for the accounting of output, sales and finished products, warehouse accounting data, production information, data on the movement of finished products between warehouses and its sale.

The basis of this analysis is a comparison of the volume indicators set by the organization's plan with the actual ones. In the intra-company analysis, the level of gross and marketable products is studied, their dynamics is studied.[4]

The indicator characterizing the result of an organization's production activity is the volume of products produced and sold. Its change is influenced by the following factors: production capacity, product orders, and the organization's availability of resources.[5] The financial position and financial result of the organization's work depend on the volume of sales. When analyzing product sales indicators, the composition and structure of manufactured products are determined.

An important indicator of the activity of industrial organizations is the quality of products, its improvement is one of their forms of competition, gaining and retaining positions in the market.[6] A high level of product quality contributes to an increase in demand for products and an increase in the amount of profit not only due to sales volume, but also due to higher prices.

In conclusion, The production and sale of finished products (works, services) is the main part of entrepreneurial activity. The finished product is a production process. Finished products can be accounted for according to the planned cost of the enterprise or in retail prices. Special attention should be paid to the specifics of calculating the cost of products ready for sale. The basis for correct calculation is a rational cost grouping. The costs can be grouped according to different criteria: by type of expenses, by type of products, by place of origin, etc. The analysis of the sale of finished products is the main control element in the organization's system and, based on the analysis, control over the production, sale, and transportation of products is ensured.

List of literature:

1. Zalilova, Z.A. Introduction of digitalization in the agro-industrial complex / Z.A. Zalilova // Innovations and technological breakthrough in agriculture: Collection of scientific papers of the international scientific and practical conference, Bryansk, November 19, 2020. Volume Part 2. – Bryansk: Bryansk State Agrarian University, 2020. – pp. 96-99.

2. Kovshov, V.A. Priorities for the formation of competitiveness of small forms of agricultural production / V.A. Kovshov // Innovative activity of science and education in agro-industrial production: materials of the International scientific and practical conference, Kursk, February 27-28, 2019 / Responsible for the release of I.Y. Pigorev.. Volume 4. – Kursk: Kursk State Agricultural Academy, 2019. – pp. 197-201.

3. Kovshov, V. A. Digital transformation of the economy of the regional agro-industrial complex / V. A. Kovshov // Russian electronic scientific journal. – 2022. – № 4(46). – Pp. 272-292.

4. Lukyanova, M.T. The role of production resources in the strategic development of enterprises / M.T. Lukyanova, V.A. Yalalutdinov // Russian Electronic Scientific Journal. – 2023. – № 3(49). – Pp. 133-146.

5. Khodkovskaya Yu.V., Malykh O.E., Fazrakhmanov I.I., Khisamutdinov I.A., Barkova E.E. Circular economy: imperatives of sustainable development of the ecosystem of the region // CITISE. 2022. No. 2 (32). Pp. 507-518.

6. Semin A., Bukhtiyarova T., Stovba E. The use of cluster and foresight technologies in the development of strategies for sustainable development of rural

areas in the region // IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering, 2020, 753(8), 082007.